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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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The Analysis of The Influence of Advertising E-commerce Paid to The Selection of Stores and Products

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Abstract. The Covid-19 pandemic has resulted in the implementation of social restrictions, including buying and selling transactions. As a result, there is an increase in the use of online buying and selling sites or e-commerce. The existence of many online stores increases competition between sellers for buyers, so sellers try to advertise. In this study investigated the effect of advertising on the selection of stores and products by customers. In addition, the factors that influence buyers when shopping at online stores are also analyzed. Quantitative data were collected by means of a questionnaire from a number of respondents. Data analysis was carried out descriptively, followed by multinomial logistic regression analysis and nonhierarchical cluster analysis and cramer's V. the Information obtained that age, gender, and income affect the presence of advertisements on a product in e-commerce. Women pay more attention to product advertisements than men. As the age of the buyer increases, the interest in advertising increases. In e-commerce stores, product descriptions and appearances are the most important factors for buyers. The better the description and appearance of the product, the better the rating and reviews.

Keywords: *E-commerce, advertising, multinomial logistic regression, cluster analysis, cramer's V*

1. Introduction

Pandemic Covid-19 that happened in the world make changes to the order of life. Socialization is often done with the meet, must now be transferred with the online system. In Indonesia, all activities pursued done from home and utilizing existing technology, such as conference online, online learning, and shopping online. These circumstances have an impact on the increase of internet users in Indonesia. Quoted from the report titled "Digital 2021" by the newspaper Kompas.com, it is known that there is an increase of 15.5% or 27 million at the beginning of the year 2021 and the data is obtained since January, 2020 [1]. In the report, internet users aged 16 to 64 years using different electronic devices. However, of all these types of devices electronics, *smartphones* became the most popular devices with percentage up 98,3% with an estimated 195,3 million people access the internet through *smartphones*. Various things can be accessed through the *smartphone* include app-the app for activities online.

Shopping online is currently one of the solution to meet the daily needs in the pandemic. In addition, by shopping online, people do not need to get out of the house so it can help reduce the number of the spread of the virus Covid-19. Based on these conditions, the data compiled by the Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS) shows that there is an increase in the sales of *e-commerce* in the month of April

2020 by 4.8 times of sales in January 2020 [2]. In addition, a survey conducted online by 504 respondents by Alvares Research Center in April 2020. In the survey, 87,1% of respondents have done shopping online, most products purchased are food and beverage [3]. The Data shows that the community is now doing a lot of shopping online.

Online trading when this can take place easily because of the many a site selling online. Several major sites today such as Shopee, Tokopedia, and others also provide services that simplify the process of buying and selling. Observations on these sites shows that today there are millions of online stores in Indonesia. Tokopedia on life span has claimed that there are 11 million online store listed. The high number of online store in Indonesia has an impact on both buyers and sellers. For buyers, the existence of many online stores give you the choice more diverse. On the contrary, for sellers, the existence of many of the online store means increasing competition among sellers to find buyers, so sellers need to make efforts to attract buyers and get keunt.

According to Shahnaz and Wahyono, buying interest is likely a consumer will make a purchase with the search for information from various sources [4]. In general, when shopping online, then the information obtained is related to the store and the product is a rating and review. In addition, the related stores will be provided informationi related to the performance speed of the reply to the message, the length of the store join the marketplace, followers stores, and other general information. While such information for most people to be one of the supporters to determine in the store where she was going shopping. It is important for the seller to know what course that became the attention of their target market when choosing a shop or product.

In this research will be analyzedis the factors that affect the buyer when shopping on the online store. The analysis used logistic regression multinomial, the analysis of the cluster method nonhierarki, and cramer's V.

2. Methods

The research is using descriptive analysis method with quantitative approach. The subject of this research is the people of Indonesia who have ever used *e-commerce* to shop online. The object of this study is the advertising of *e-commerce* paid. The Data used is primary data obtained from the 363 respondents who fill out a four-part questionnaire, namely sociodemographic respondents, the experience of the respondents in the use of *e-commerce*, 10 questions about the factors that affect buyers in choosing products *e-commerce* with answers in the form of four options (never, rarely, often, always), and 14 questions about the factors that affect buyers in select stores *e-commerce* with answers in the form of four options (never, rarely, often, always), the Respondents fill in the questionnaire provided by the provisions of the score as follows.

The perfect	Score
is Always	4
Often	3
Rarely	2
never	1

Furthermore, the data will be visualized with a *stacked bar chart* and will be done if the data using logistic regression multinomial to determine the results of the analysis in the form of opportunities. The analysis of regression logistic multinomial done to find the relationship of the variables of the response scale nominal with the variable the dependent form of data qualitative shaped multinomial. The data will be determined the relationship between the ad with the conditions of sociodemographic buyer and determine the opportunities of the level of the tendency of the buyer against ads based on variables that are significant. On logistic regression multinomial, the variables used are polikotomus or

multinomial model with

$$\pi(x) = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_bx_b)}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_bx_b)}$$

[5].

The next stage is to do if the data returned by the analysis of *cluster* methods nonhierarki with the aim that the variables can be grouped. The data will be determined *clusters* on the factors that affect buyers in choosing products in *e-commerce* and store than in *e-commerce* based on the income and type of gender.

While for the analysis of *cluster* or group analysis aims to classify *i=object* into several groups that there are differences in the properties so that the object has properties that are relatively homogeneous [6]. *Cluster-a cluster* that has the characteristic homogeneous among its members and heterogeneous to *cluster a* to *cluster* the other. For the analysis of nonhierarki, then it will use *K-means clustering*. *K-Means clustering*, one of the methods of analysis of *cluster* nonhierarki that classify the data into the in the form of *clusters* with characteristics that are the same. The method of *K-Means* used as effective and efficient if used in grouping the data with a number that large.

Furthermore, the analysis will be continued by using the analysis of *cramer's V*, which is the coefficient of correlation between the two categories where the category of the scale nominal. The data will be determined the coefficient of correlation between the factors that affect buyers in the choose products in *e-commerce* and store online on *e-commerce*. The results of the analysis of the *cramer's V* will be visualized using a heatmap. A *Heatmap* is a way to mempresentasikan data with the form of map or diagram and the value is depicted by the intensity of the color. The high number correlation, the color will be more dark.

3. Result

3.1. Descriptive Dana and Respondents

Figure 1. Factors that affect buyers in choosing products in *e-commerce*

Figure 2. Factors that affect buyers in choosing a store online in *e-commerce*

Data obtained by distributing questionnaires online to the respondents who are the people of Indonesia who use *e-commerce*. The Data collected as many as 363 data, data processing performed with the aid of a *software* Program R. From 363 data is known that Shopee into *e-commerce* with frequent use it is aligned with the *Map of E-commerce* Q4 2021 's iPrice [7]. Respondents with the kind of sex women who dominate the result in the category of products most purchased namely: *fashion*, care and beauty. Factors that are considered buyers in choosing a store is *rating* of products and review the product, while the advertising of products and product search top into factors that are less noticed. In select stores, a factor that is considered the buyer is free postage sent, *the rating of the store*, and many discount stores.

3.2. The Analysis of Logistic Regression Multinomial

The following is the analysis of regresi logistic multinomial on the decision of the shop through the shop online by watching ads. Based on the analysis of the regression logistic multinomial obtained by the age, type of sex, and income effect against the tendency of the buyer against ad in buying a product in *e-commerce*. Will but, the level of education, level of experience buyers in using *e-commerce*, and the intensity of the shopping buyer is not influential.

Figure 3. The relationship of age and ads in men

Figure 4. The relationship of age and ad in women

Types of gender and age significantly. From Image 3 and Image 4 we know that women are more interested to advertising *e-commerce* compared to men. However, the old age of the buyer then will the reduced interest against advertising *e-commerce*.

On the modeling type of the sexes and income with advertising as a variable dependent. Obtained the value of the alleged opportunities to calculate the chances of the tendency of the buyer against ad based on the type of gender and earnings aimed at Tabel 1, with the equations of the alleged chances are as the following.

$$\pi_{never} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{0.93+0.57x_1+0.69x_2^S+0.76x_2^T} + e^{0.67+0.52x_1+0.3x_2^S+0.41x_2^T} + e^{-1.63+1.4x_1+0.72x_2^S+1.6x_2^T}} \quad (1)$$

$$\pi_{Rarely} = \frac{e^{0.93+0.57x_1+0.69x_2^S+0.76x_2^T}}{1 + e^{0.93+0.57x_1+0.69x_2^S+0.76x_2^T} + e^{0.67+0.52x_1+0.3x_2^S+0.41x_2^T} + e^{-1.63+1.4x_1+0.72x_2^S+1.6x_2^T}} \quad (2)$$

$$\pi_{Often} = \frac{e^{0.67+0.52x_1+0.3x_2^S+0.41x_2^T}}{1 + e^{0.93+0.57x_1+0.69x_2^S+0.76x_2^T} + e^{0.67+0.52x_1+0.3x_2^S+0.41x_2^T} + e^{-1.63+1.4x_1+0.72x_2^S+1.6x_2^T}} \quad (3)$$

$$\pi_{Always} = \frac{e^{-1.63+1.4x_1+0.72x_2^S+1.6x_2^T}}{1 + e^{0.93+0.57x_1+0.69x_2^S+0.76x_2^T} + e^{0.67+0.52x_1+0.3x_2^S+0.41x_2^T} + e^{-1.63+1.4x_1+0.72x_2^S+1.6x_2^T}} \quad (4)$$

Table 1. Opportunities the level of the tendency of the buyer against ad based on the type of sex and income

Earnings	Men				Women			
	There never	Rarely	Often	Always	Not never	Rarely	Often	Always
Low	0,18	0,44	0,34	0,04	0,11	0,47	0,34	0,08
Are	0,11	0,55	0,29	0,05	0,06	0,56	0,28	0,10
High	0,09	0,52	0,29	0,10	0,05	0,49	0,26	0,20

On the table above looks that buyers are men and women that income low, medium, or high tend to be rare in consider ads when they buy products in *e-commerce*.

3.3. The analysis of Cluster Methods Non-Hierarchy

Based on the methods *silhouette* to determine the k optimal is obtained that as much as 2 *clusters* are formed. On the *cluster* first , there are 220 respondents and cluster the second there were 143 respondents. Factors that into the consideration of the buyers in choosing a product and store on *cluster 1* and *cluster 2* can be seen on picture 3, 4, and 5.

Based on the results of the analysis of cluster nonhierarchy on the data overall, the data based on the type of gender, and income can be seen on Tabel 2.

Table 2. The factors are considered and ignored the buyer in selecting a product and a store in *e-commerce*

Data	Level	Category of	Factors	
			Considered	Negligible
Overall		Product	Rating, reviews, and display product	Ads and product search top
		Store	Free shipping send, the discount, and <i>the rating of the store</i>	Ads and <i>followers</i> shop
Types Gender	Men	Product	<i>rating</i> , review, view, and the description of the product	Advertising and product search top
		Store	free shipping send, the discount, and <i>the rating of the store</i>	Advertising
	the Women's	Product	<i>rating</i> , review, view, and description of product	Advertising and product search top
		Store	free shipping send, discount, and <i>the rating of the store</i>	Advertising
Revenue	Low	Product	<i>ratings</i> , reviews, description, display, and product best-selling	advertising products and product search top
		Store	free shipping send, the discount, and <i>the rating of the store</i>	Advertising
	Are	Product	<i>rating</i> , reviews, description, and the appearance of the product	price of the product, product search top
		Store	free shipping send, discount product and <i>the rating of the store</i>	Advertising

a High Product *rating*, review, view, Discounts, prices, and
 and description of advertising
 product
 Store free postage to send Ads
 and *rating* shop

3.4. Cramer's V

Furthermore, the analysis will proceed by using the analysis of Cramer's V, which is visualized using a heatmap.

Figure 5. The coefficient of correlation between the category of factors that affect buyers in choosing products in e-commerce

Figure 6. The coefficient of correlation between the category of factors that affect buyers in choosing a store online in e-commerce

Based on Image 5 looks that description product related in moderate to rating the product, review the product, the appearance of the image of the product. If the description of products is getting better

and the appearance of the image of its products more attractive then rating the product will be the good as well as reviews of the product would be the better also.

Based on Image 6 looks that free postage to send and discount stores have a relationship. It this means the decision of the buyer in choosing a store online is not only based on the free postage sent, but rather the presence of discount else in the store is.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the penany years of research that has been done canat be concluded that the regression multinomial used to analyze the relationship between the ad with the conditions of sociodemographic the buyer. Obtained age, type of sex, and income effect against the presence of advertising on a product in *e-commerce*. Women are more mindful of advertisement products than men. Along with the increasing age of the buyer then the interest on the presence of ad increased. In the store *e-commerce*, description and appearance of the product to be the factor that most note buyers. The better the description and appearance of the products it will be better also rating and review.

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